

Drawing Graphs of Differentiable Functions with STACK and JSXGraph using Hermite Splines

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Abstract: Curve sketching is a typical problem in elementary as well as in advanced mathematics. It is even more complex to implement in computer-aided assessment if instant sketches on demand should be possible. This paper introduces an approach using STACK and JSXGraph based on Hermite splines that faces this problem. In addition to central aspects of both the implementation in JavaScript and the evaluation in Maxima, it will point out the didactical potential of the approach including experiences from a first trial.

Keywords: JSXGraph, Hermite splines, curve sketching, graphs of functions, Tall, three worlds of mathematics

1 Introduction

The introduction of modern technologies into university teaching has opened up new possibilities for designing tasks. An important subset of these are digital exercises, as they can be realized in STACK. Here, randomized tasks can be constructed, with which students can practice online as often as they want [BR18]. Didactically challenging tasks can be developed, ranging from adaptive feedback [We19], the integration of interactive H5P videos [Al19], external adaptive flow control [Br17], in which learners are guided to easier or more difficult tasks depending on their results, internal adaptive flow control by reacting adaptively to incorrect intermediate results within tasks [Al20], to the integration of dynamic geometry [Kl19]. The integration of dynamic geometry opens the door for challenging conceptual tasks combining symbolic and embodied representation forms as well as for innovative enhancements using JavaScript. In the following section 2 a brief overview is given about the motivational background for developing these tasks. Section 3 summarizes existing ways of implementing curve sketching in computer-aided assessment and sections 4 and 5 are then describing our approach of using Hermite splines. In the concluding section 6 results are summarized and an outlook on further developments is given.

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2 Tall's three worlds of mathematics as a starting point for designing tasks with multiple representation forms

Tall (2004) described that learning takes place in three worlds of mathematics, namely, in an embodied world, a symbolic world, and a formal world. In the embodied world, learners make use of a concept's physical attributes combined with their sensual experiences to build mental concepts. The symbolic world is where the symbolic representations of concepts are specified and where it is possible to "switch effortlessly from processes to do mathematics, to concepts to think about" [Ta04, p. 30]. The formal world "builds from lists of axioms expressed formally through sequences of theorems proved deductively with the intention of building a coherent formal knowledge structure" [Ta10, p. 22]. In this work, we focus on the symbolic and embodied worlds and the intersection of the two. Here, a concept, a solution process, a symbolic representation as well as an embodied representation or manifestation of the learning object exist. The goal of teaching, of course, is always that students build connections between these points as marked in Fig. 1, and not just memorize the solution process and learn it by rote. In the example shown in Fig. 1, students are confronted with the concept of derivation. Learners can only solve the task if they have understood the concept in the symbolic and embodied worlds and can connect the two worlds. The concept and solution process are hidden here, while the

Fig. 1: STACK task with visible representations in the symbolic and embodied worlds while the underlying concept and solution process are invisible (own implementation)

symbolic and embodied representations, or at least parts of them, are visible. In a next step, we wondered what learners would do if we also make the symbolic world invisible in similar tasks as shown in Fig. 2. This task can only be solved by geometric reasoning because values and the symbolic representation of the function by means of a function rule are not visible. We could observe that many students try to make the symbolic world visible (Fig. 3). They try to use the symbolic world as a scaffold, even when this is not possible, e.g. due to a missing correspondence between input and output values as in the

posed task. For this reason, the idea of constructing more tasks of this type arose and to develop some new features for STACK tasks like curve sketching to realize it.

Fig. 2: Task with visible representation form in the embodied world while the representation in the symbolic world, the concept and solution process are invisible (own implementation)

Fig. 3: Students tend to try to make the symbolic world visible as a scaffold even if this is not possible

3 Curve Sketching in Digital Assessment

In many subject areas, especially in calculus, graphs of functions are important elements of the embodied world. With Maxima's `plot2d` command (which is only `plot` in STACK) and the JavaScript library JSXGraph STACK offers various options to display randomized graphs within a STACK question. Including in-time and on demand drawing of function graphs in a task is more difficult though. It is involving two aspects: the implementation of a suitable drawing tool and the automatic evaluation and provision of

feedback. Especially the latter is challenging because it will normally include some interpretation: Is the graph really touching the x -axis or does it just come close, is the function not differentiable at a certain point or does it just have a “steep” slope ...? In addition to the approach presented in sections 4 and 5 there are at least three different ways to implement curve sketching in STACK:

- **Multiple choice questions**

Providing different function graphs as options of a multiple choice question is probably the easiest way to transfer tasks that include curve sketching, to computer-aided assessment. Since the options are given by the teacher, no interpretation of the answer is needed and one can give detailed feedback on the student’s answer [Ba20]. On the other hand, this approach is going along with typical problems of multiple choice questions such as eliminating incorrect options or verifying properties of the correct graph [Sa13, SJ17] instead of mentally constructing the correct answer. Not least, the dynamic character of these tasks is completely lost.

- **Transformations of given types of functions**

Some questions already presume that the function graph asked is of a specific type, i.e. a linear, a quadratic or a trigonometric function. In this case, teachers can provide a dynamic graph of an elementary function of this type that students then can transform by dragging one or several points with a mouse (Fig. 4). This approach is closer to natural drawing because transforming the given plot is a dynamic process

Fig. 4: Example of a STACK question including a transformation of a given function graph (own implementation)

and there are unlimited possible answers. Such as with multiple choice questions detailed feedback can be provided. However, this type of question is still reducing the complexity of a paper-based drawing task. Students only have to consider some properties of a graph that all have close correspondents in the symbolic world: Where is the vertex of the parabola? In which direction does it open? What is the

vertical/horizontal shrink? Students do not need to think about the characteristic shape of the curve though. For example, what is the slope of the tangent line at any other point but the vertex? In addition, of course, this approach can only deal with a given function type or, if providing a menu with several function types³, with transformations of elementary functions.

- **Freehand sketches**

Freehand sketches are a direct transfer of paper-based drawing tasks to computer-aided assessment. Here no limitations regarding the function type are made and students can sketch any curve. [MM18] introduced a task using this approach based on STACK and JSXGraph. They interpret the student's answer as a set of points and provide feedback on the accuracy of the sketch. They also report on some limitations regarding feedback in their prototype, such as referencing the correct shape of a graph that is not located close to the correct answer. Using a pen "feels more natural than using a mouse" [MM18, p. 3].

In the next section, we describe a way that encompasses some of the weaknesses described above by using Hermite splines.

4 Using Hermite splines to draw graphs of differentiable functions

4.1 Why using Hermite Splines?

With the approaches summarized in section 3, there is already a variety of approaches to implement curve sketching in digital assessment. Why developing yet another one? Our motivation to develop the tool was based on three aspects: First, Hermite splines are a

Fig. 5: Sketch of the graph of the exponential function using points and tangent lines compared with a computer plot of the function

well-known tool in computer graphics and therefore the method suggests itself to be used for digital curve sketching. Second, the approach can nicely be handled with any input method, being mouse or pen or finger. And third, and most important, drawing graphs of

³ The assessment system MyMathLab is using this method to realize drawing tasks (https://dahn-research.eu/Survey/fr_studierende25.html)

functions should include both function values and derivatives, points and tangent lines, which is exactly what Hermite splines do. Many mathematical functions, such as the trigonometric functions, the exponential or logarithmic function, have typical and important properties of their derivatives; using these properties by drawing some tangent lines leads to precise graphs (Fig. 5).

4.2 Mathematical background

Given the values and the first derivatives of a differentiable function f at $n + 1$ points $P_0(x_0, f(x_0)), \dots, P_n(x_n, f(x_n))$, Hermite splines approximate f piecewise by polynomials $p_1(x), \dots, p_n(x)$ (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Example of a Hermite spline

These satisfy

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_i(x_{i-1}) &= f(x_{i-1}) \\
 p_i(x_i) &= f(x_i) \\
 p_i'(x_{i-1}) &= f'(x_{i-1}) \\
 p_i'(x_i) &= f'(x_i)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Higher derivatives may be included by adding respective conditions. In the theory of cubic Hermite splines, $p_1(x), \dots, p_n(x)$ are expressed by so-called Hermite basis functions, which gives an effective solution to the problem.⁴ However, in our task we are using the “elementary approach” of solving the n systems of linear equations given by (1). This allows to flexibly switch to polynomials of degrees greater than three if needed. If sticking with cubic polynomials the spline P is continuously differentiable only once, i.e. $P \in C^1$.

5 Example question

5.1 Description

To put the approach into practice, we picked the problem of graphical differentiation: Students are given the graph of a randomized polynomial of fifth degree, each with two

⁴ For details, for example see [Go03].

local extrema and one saddle point (Fig. 7) and they are to find the graph of the derivative. In order to do this they can modify and extend a given Hermite spline that only consists of two points (so-called anchor points) and a constant function. Every anchor point has

Fig. 7: Example question, unanswered

two handles to control the slope. Hence, students can change both the function values and the slopes of the tangent lines. They can add more anchor points, remove a selected point or reset the whole graph. Before submitting or in order to better check the answer, students can hide the anchor points.

After students have submitted their question, STACK is evaluating the answer and providing feedback⁵. The specific feedback is including information on the interval (Is the domain of f' covered?), positions and types of the zeroes (touching or intersecting the x -axis), stationary points and both signs and function values at the stationary points and endpoints of the interval. When feedback is being displayed, students can also show the correct graph of f' in addition to their answer. In order to check their own or the correct answer, they can also display a movable tangent line to the graph of f (Fig. 8).

⁵ For details on the implementation, see the following subsections.

Tidy STACK question tool | Question tests & deployed variat

Given the graph of $f : [-3, 3] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ (grey graph) find the graph of the derivative function f' of f .

In order to sketch the graph of f' modify the blue graph. You can change function values and tangent lines slopes by dragging the respective points. You can also add more anchor points.

► Usage notes

! You have correctly depicted some but not all properties of the graph of f' .
 You have depicted the zeros of f' at the right points. However, you haven't correctly distinguished between points of intersecting and points of touching the x -axis.
 Notice that the graph of f' is intersecting the x -axis where f is changing its monotonic behaviour.
 The **exact graph** of f' can now be plotted above in addition to your answer.

Fig. 8: Example question, answered and with feedback

5.2 Implementation with JSXGraph and JavaScript

The drawing tool is implemented using JavaScript and especially the library JSXGraph in the question text. Every time an anchor point or a handle is moved, the neighbouring graphs (in case of the first and the last anchor point there is only one) are updated. This process consists of the following steps: (1) Determining the coefficient matrix of the system of linear equations, (2) solving the linear system using Gauss elimination, (3) redefining the polynomial on the respective interval and (4) updating the graph on this interval. In our example question, we have only used cubic polynomials until now.

The coefficients of the polynomials and the coordinates of the anchor points and handles

are stored in two hidden STACK inputs, a third input is reserved for additional properties, such as the visibility of the anchor points.

5.3 Evaluation with STACK

In the feedback variables the student's answer is interpreted and defined as a piecewise function. This allows to compute various properties of this function: zeroes and their multiplicities, stationary points, signs and absolute values of the output at certain points. These properties are compared with the teacher's answer in the potential response tree (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9: Potential response tree of the example question

Although these computations can be performed straight forward by the computer algebra system Maxima, there are some tricky issues to be aware of:

- Stationary points close to the x -axis**
 A graph might look like touching the x -axis at a local maximum or minimum point, but in fact there might be no zero, one (as probably intended by the student) or two zeroes. Hence, local maximum or minimum points with an extremum close to zero should be interpreted as zeroes.
- Zeroes close to the endpoints of a subinterval**
 If an anchor point is located close to the x -axis then due to numerical tolerances Maxima may find a zero in none, one or both of its neighbouring subintervals. Therefore, it is important to expand the interval for finding the zeroes of one polynomial and to merge close zeroes. This is also relevant for stationary points close to the x -axis (see above).
- Tolerances**
 Every answer test is using a certain tolerance, i.e. students already receive full score if their graph is somewhat close to the teachers answer. To compare positions (of zeroes or stationary points) we are only using absolute tolerances. For function values it is important though to include both absolute and relative tolerances. For numbers

with a “high” absolute value we are using a relative, for numbers with a “small” absolute value an absolute tolerance (plus the sign). Currently we consider absolute values less than 0.2 as small.

5.4 Experiences

We have proven our example question in a first term mathematics lecture for engineering students. Students had several attempts and most of them created a meaningful graph already in their first try, indicating that they got along with the tool. Some graphs had extra inflection points or were looking somewhat angular, i.e. they included sectors with a small radius of curvature – two aspects for which feedback has not yet been implemented in the current version. The automatic feedback was working for typical errors like incorrect zeroes, wrong signs of the derivative function or horizontal tangent lines at the endpoints of the interval, but not every attempt received meaningful feedback yet. Some of these issues can be resolved by a thorough selection of deployed variants, others need further development (see section 6). Finally, there were also students who succeeded in “drawing” a graph that was really close to the actual derivative function and received full score.

6 Discussion

We think that using Hermite splines to transfer drawing tasks to computer-aided assessment can add some extra value to the existing approaches (see section 3). Students can answer such a question with different input methods, such as mouse, finger or digital pen, and easily adapt their answer. Using Hermite splines allows drawing graphs that are very close to the teacher’s answer, which can be motivating when receiving feedback. Including both points and derivatives, the approach also adds didactic value to curve sketching tasks.

Regarding feedback and evaluation, teachers know that the students entered the graph of a differentiable function, because this is what the tool allows, and they do not have to perform additional analysis such as polynomial regression. Moreover, the functional equation to the student’s graph can directly be used to compute various properties of the function. Hence, opportunities for feedback are rich. At the same time, it is complex to get feedback robust. Here we see potential for further developments. It would be good to include feedback on inflection points and sectors with a small radius of curvature. In addition, based on the attempts from the trial we can now optimize the tolerances used. In particular, the margin for zeroes should depend on the derivative at the zero, because some stationary points can be located more precise than others can. One disadvantage of the approach is its somehow limited applicability. Knowing that Hermite splines are approximating differentiable functions, the method does not work for functions with non-differentiability points, discontinuities or singularities.

It is an open question for research if and how the different methods for digital curve sketching are influencing student’s understanding of central concepts of functions.

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